

Designing Illustrated Children's Book for Elementary Student as a Media to Introduce Lurik

Hanifa Budi Wardani¹, Esty Wulandari²

¹(Department of Visual Communication Design, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Indonesia)

²(Department of Visual Communication Design, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT : Weaving is the result of past cultures that still exist today. One area that has distinctive woven fabrics is Java, Indonesia with its lurik. Besides Surakarta and Yogyakarta, lurik is also produced in Klaten. Fans of this lurik also come from various regions and even abroad. However, there are still people who don't even know about lurik, especially children. Children's lack of knowledge about lurik encourages the importance of early introduction and education about lurik. Preservation of Indonesia's local culture is an important thing to do. Efforts to preserve lurik have been carried out by various parties, but the younger generation who are the successors of the nation is a hope for the nation to be able to preserve the existing culture. The right communication media is needed to introduce lurik to the younger generation, especially children. One of the media that can be used is picture story books. The type of research conducted is descriptive qualitative research. This study aims to design children's book as a medium for introducing lurik for elementary student.

KEYWORDS –children's book, education, elementary student, illustration, lurik

I. INTRODUCTION

Weaving is the result of past cultures that still exist today. According to the records of the Tenun Ikat Indonesia catalog in Museum Nasional (2000), weaving techniques that entered Indonesia probably came from mainland Southeast Asia, with looms that use wooden supports at the waist (middle back) (Museum Tekstil Jakarta, 2013: 1-2). Although it is not an indigenous culture of the Indonesian nation, weaving of the archipelago has developed and has its own characteristics. This can be seen from the uniqueness of the pattern and variety of weaving in various regions.

One area that has distinctive woven fabrics is Java with its lurik. The word lurik comes from the Javanese lorek or lurik which means line. Lurik is the result of textile crafts that are closely related to the time of the Keraton Kartasura until after it was divided into Kasultanan Yogyakarta and Kasunanan Surakarta. Lurik are generally used for daily wear. However, striated patterns / motifs are also distinguished for the Keraton and the general public (Suprayitno & Ariesta, 2014: 844). Over time, in addition to Surakarta and Yogyakarta, lurik also developed in the surrounding area, one of which is Klaten.

Lurik Klaten, the forerunner of which was Lurik Pedan which was pioneered by a rich merchant named Suhardi Hadi Sumarto (Kemdikbud.go.id, 2021). In its glory, which was around 1950-1960, lurik were in demand. But then began to decline during the Soeharto reign due to modernization and conglomeration. The use of ATBM (Non-Machine Loom) began to switch to machines.

Although the use of machine looms is an alternative in meeting market demand for lurik, there are several lurik production sites in Klaten that still use ATBM. This is a special value for lurik produced because they are thick with the cultural value of ancestral heritage. Fans of this lurik also come from various regions and even abroad. However, there are still people who don't even know about lurik, especially children.

Lurik is one of the Indonesia's cultural heritages that should be preserved. Conservation efforts have been carried out by various parties, ranging from the government to the community. The sustainability of a

culture also depends on the younger generation as the successor of the nation. There needs to be a means of communication that can reach more young people, especially children. This is expected to be able to instill a love for local culture so that the existence of lurik can be closer to the community and still exist and develop in the future.

Based on these descriptions, it is important to create a communication medium for children as an effort to introduce lurik. One of them is through children's book. Simple stories and visualizations through illustrations can attract children's attention. Through children's book, children can love reading more so that reading becomes fun. This is an opportunity to be able to introduce culture through children's book. With the existence of children's book entitle "Membuat Lurik Di Rumah Nenek" that introduce lurik, it is hoped that the community, especially children, can get to know lurik better and grow a sense of pride and love for the local traditions around them.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Children's Book

There are various types of children's books. Children's books also provide various benefits for children's cognitive development. Farihatin (in Putri, Iswantiningtyas, & Widayati, 2022: 692) revealed that by reading using books that have interesting pictures can increase children to explore the contents of the books in the children's book, basic skills can also be obtained by getting used to inviting children to read books together at home and accompanied by parents, especially in books that have pictures can grow children's reading skills.

2.2 Illustration

Illustration comes from the Latin *ilustrare* which means to explain something. So what is meant by illustration is drawing with the aim of clarifying an object visually so that the reading content is easily understood by readers, such as pictures found in print media and textbooks (RM & Siswandi, 2008: 30). Another opinion on illustration was put forward by Martin Salisbury. Martin Salisbury (in Kartaatmadja, 2015: 148) argues that illustration is the first means for children to understand a world that they have not fully experienced. Illustrations have varied functions. According to Utari (sumber.belajar.kemdikbud.go.id) illustration has the following functions: attract the attention of its readers in terms of the colors displayed; make it easier to understand a description or explanation that there are several characters featured in the story; as a means of expressing the experience of an event expressed in an image; provide a brief overview of the content of the writing or story submitted; as the value of beauty in the face.

2.3 Lurik

The word lurik is rooted in the Javanese word *lorek* which means lines also with the word *lirik*, which means lines, but the lines are small (Wahyono in Wuryani: 2013: 84). Wuryani explained that etymologically speaking, the "i" sound in lurik is to designate the meaning of small lines that are transverse and longitudinal. As in Javanese in general when mentioning something small, such as; *dicuwil* (*nyuwil*), *dijiwit*, *klithik*, *benthik*, and so on which have a small meaning. In ancient times, lurik was closely related to the life of the Javanese. Lurik is often used as clothing to the required cloth in traditional ceremonies.

III. METHODOLOGY

The research method used in this study is descriptive qualitative. This type of qualitative research has a descriptive nature and tends to use analysis. The process and meaning are highlighted more in this type of research with a theoretical foundation that is used as a guiding source so that the focus of research is in accordance with the facts in the field (Ramdhan, 2021: 6). The purpose of qualitative research methods is to explain an event or phenomenon by collecting in-depth data.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 *Lurik* and the Manufacturing Process

Striated cloth in ancient Javanese terms is called lurik which means row, line or strip. Another opinion says lurik comes from the word rik which means line or trench, which can mean as a fence or protector for the wearer (Adji & Wahyuningsih, 2018: 130). In Javanese etymology, the sound "i" in lurik is to designate the meaning of small lines that are transverse and longitudinal (Wuryani, 2013: 84). Wahyono (in Purwaningsih, 2022: 129) argues that lurik are woven fabrics whose decorations are longitudinal, transverse, or a combination of the two.

The author interviewed an employee of one of the lurik production sites in Klaten. She explained the process of making lurik which begins with preparing the yarn. Likas is a yarn in the form of coils in cones, processed into hank, to facilitate the penetration of dyes into the yarn. The yarn dyeing process is still done manually. The process is called celup/wenter. The yarn that has dried will then go through a klos process. Klos or rewinding is the process of rolling yarn back from hank to cones. Ramadhani and Sukmawan explained that the purpose of the kelos (klos) process is to improve the quality of yarn and arrange the shape of the yarn coil according to the next process to be carried out.

The next process is sekir or warping. This warping is the process of making or arranging motifs or patterns of fabric according to order. After warping, the thread will enter the cucuk process. Cucuk is the process of inserting threads one by one into droppers, guns, and combs before entering the weaving process. After going through the cucuk, then enter the weaving process using a loom. In the weaving machine, there is a palet process which is the process of rolling weft yarn into bobbin/klenteng.

4.2 Elementary Student's Knowledge about *Lurik*

To determine the extent of lurik knowledge in elementary school children, the author made observations in two public elementary schools in Klaten. Based on observations made, it is known that of the total respondents as many as 57.9% of respondents have never heard of lurik, as many as 26.9% of respondents have heard several times, and 15.2% others often hear about lurik.

Figure 4.2.1 Results of questionnaire on students' knowledge of lurik

Although some respondents have heard of lurik, it is known that as many as 74.5% of all respondents do not know what lurik is, but as many as 21.4% know enough and 4.1% know very much about lurik. This shows that lurik is still less known among elementary school children.

In addition, the author also made observations to find out respondents' knowledge about the process of making lurik. The result is that as many as 86.9% of respondents do not know about the process of making lurik, 10.3% of respondents have known enough, and 2.1% of respondents have been very knowledgeable. The data obtained shows that there is still a lack of education about lurik in elementary students, especially about the process of making lurik.

4.3 Children's Book Visual Concept

The author compiled the visual concept of a children's book entitled "Membuat Lurik Di Rumah Nenek" which aims to introduce lurik to elementary school children. The concept was made based on the results of a questionnaire about the interests and tastes of elementary school children related to children's books. The results of the questionnaire play a big role in the design of the story characters, color selection, and the type of font to be used.

Character Design

Characters are selected based on the results of questionnaires regarding the appearance of the preferred character. There are four characters who play a lot of roles in the story, namely Sasa, Grandma, Father, and Mother.

Picture 4.3.1 Character line up (from left: Father, Mother, Sasa, Grandma)

Typography

Fonts with simple shapes are chosen as body text in children's book so that children can easily understand the text. Nunito font was chosen as the body text in this book. Milonga font is used as the headline. This font was chosen based on the results of the questionnaire that had been distributed.

Nunito											Milonga										
Aa	Bb	Cc	Dd	Ee	Ff	Gg	Hh	Ii	Jj		Aa	Bb	Cc	Dd	Ee	Ff	Gg	Hh	Ii	Jj	
Kk	Ll	Mm	Nn	Oo	Pp	Qq	Rr	Ss	Tt		Kk	Ll	Mm	Nn	Oo	Pp	Qq	Rr	Ss	Tt	
Uu	Vv	Ww	Xx	Yy	Zz						Uu	Vv	Ww	Xx	Yy	Zz					
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	
!	@	#	%	^	&	*	()	-	_		!	@	#	%	^	&	*	()	-	_	
=	+	,	.	?	:	"	/	<>	[]		=	+	,	.	?	:	"	/	<>	[]	

Picture 4.3. 2 Nunito and Milonga as fonts used for the book

Colour Palette

This children's book uses a mix of warm colors to portray the atmosphere in the story. The colors used will be dominated by shades of green, yellow, and brown with a combination of other colors to be able to attract the attention of readers who are children.

Picture 4.3. 3 Colour palette used for the book

Logo

The logo used in this picture storybook is a type of logo type and uses the Milonga font. The colors used are a combination of brown, yellow, and orange.

Picture 4.3. 4 Logo for children's book "Membuat Lurik Di Rumah Nenek"

4.4 Book's Content

This book tells the story of a little girl who is attracted to *lurik* after she gets a gift of *alurik* dress from her grandmother on her birthday. The main character will visit Grandma's house to learn how to make *lurik*. The storyline will also contain information about *lurik*, such as examples of *lurik* motifs, types of looms used in *lurik* production, and the process of making *lurik*.

Picture 4.4. 1 Sketches for book's front cover (left) and book's content sample (right)

V. CONCLUSION

People, especially children, do not know much about *lurik* and many of them are still unfamiliar with *lurik*. This makes efforts to introduce *lurik* to children a necessary thing to continue. Children's book as a literacy media that children love can be the right medium to introduce *lurik*. In making a children's book about *lurik*, interesting story characters are needed, the use of colors that suit children's tastes, and the selection of the right type of font. Characters with visuals that are familiar with what children see in everyday life become characters that many children choose to become characters in the book. Children also tend to like bright and

warm colors so that they display a cheerful impression on the visuals of the book. In addition, the type of font that looks unique is chosen by many children. The design of promotional media is also carried out as a supporting media for children's book. The supporting media chosen are posters, stickers, keychains, pins, totebags, tumblrs, book label stickers, notebooks, and social media.

REFERENCES

- [1] Museum Tekstil Jakarta. 2013. Sekilas Cerita Tenun. Jakarta: Museum Tekstil Jakarta.
- [2] Suprayitno, & Ariesta, I. 2014. Makna Simbolik Dibalik Kain Lurik Solo-Yogyakarta. HUMANIORA Vol.5 No.2, 842-851.
- [3] Kemdikbud.go.id. Lurik Klaten. Warisan Budaya Tak Benda: <https://warisanbudaya.kemdikbud.go.id/?newdetail&detailTetap=2130#>. (Accessed on 25 Februari 2023 at 21.05 WIB).
- [4] Putri, E. N., Iswantiningtyas, V., & Widayati, S. R. 2022. Mengembangkan Kemampuan Membaca Pada Anak Melalui Media Buku Cerita Bergambar. Prosiding SEMDIKJAR Vol.5 (2022): SEMDIKJAR 5, 690-698.
- [5] Yoyok RM., & Siswandi. 2008. Pendidikan Seni Budaya Kelas VIII SMP. Yudhistira Ghalia Indonesia.
- [6] Kartaatmadja, H. 2015. Studi Ilustrasi Karakter Anak Indonesia untuk Rekomendasi Pembuatan Buku Cergam Anak. Tesis. Jakarta: Universitas Trisakti.
- [7] Utari, I. Menggambar Ilustrasi. <https://sumber.belajar.kemdikbud.go.id/repos/FileUpload/Seni%20Budaya%20Ilustrasi-BB/Topik-1.html>. (Accessed on 11 Maret 2023 at 15.23 WIB).
- [8] Wuryani, S. 2013. Lurik Dan Fungsinya Di Masa Lalu. Ornamen Vol.10 No.1, 81-100.
- [9] Ramdhan, M. 2021. Metode Penelitian. Surabaya: Cipta Media Nusantara.
- [10] Adji, P. S., & Wahyuningsih, N. 2018. Kain Lurik: Upaya Pelestarian Kearifan Lokal. ATRAT Vol.6 No.2, 129-136.
- [11] Purwaningsih, L. 2022. Relasi Motif Kain Lurik Jawa dan Makna Spiritualitasnya: Kajian Filosofis, Sosiologis, dan Fenomenologis. Concept: Journal of Social Humanities and Education Vol.1, No.4, 127-136.